

Nonrelativistic Limit of Dirac Equation Equivalent to Third Order Expansion of Relativistic Wave Equations?

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In (1), a modified Schrodinger equation, with an extra $a \nabla \cdot \nabla W$, is introduced to account for the nonrelativistic limit of the Dirac wavefunction: $(W, \sqrt{a} \sigma \cdot \nabla W)$, where σ is a vector of Pauli matrices. This modified Schrodinger equation gives rise to different energy levels (than the usual Schrodinger equation) and the square well potential and oscillator are considered. The wavefunction itself in these two cases retains the same math form because the mass changes to a function including a , where $a=1/(4m)$.

In (2) and (3), we proposed a general scheme for expanding a relativistic equation (such as the Klein-Gordon equation etc) in negative (not necessarily integer) powers of m . We applied this to the square well potential in (2) and the oscillator in (3). This approach yields corrections to the Schrodinger equation to any order, and also to the Schrodinger wavefunction because it uses $W_{relativistic} = W_0 + W_1 + W_2$, where W_0 is the Schrodinger wavefunction, while W_1 is a correction corresponding to a higher negative power of m and so forth.

We show here that the approach of (1) yields consistent energy values when expanding in negative powers of m to the approach of (2),(3). We consider a comparison to three orders here.

Approach of (1)

The approach of (1) is based on taking the nonrelativistic limit of the Dirac equation, which yields the 4 vector composed of two 2-spinors

$$\{ W, \sigma \cdot p / 2m W \} \quad ((1))$$

Here σ is a vector composed of the three 2x2 Pauli matrices. W is the Schrodinger wavefunction.

((1)) leads to a probability density: $W^\dagger W$ of:

$$W^* W + a \nabla W \cdot \nabla W \quad \text{where } a = 1/(4m) \quad ((2))$$

(Note: the Pauli matrices anticommute and $\sigma(i)\sigma(i)$ no sum on $i = 1$.)

A modified Schrodinger equation is then proposed in (1) to account for this situation, namely:

$$0 = -\nabla^2 W + p^2/2m W - i \partial_t W + a (i \partial_t \nabla) \cdot \nabla W \quad ((3))$$

One may see that the mathematical form of the correction in ((3)) is of the same form as the kinetic energy term, so one essentially has an effective mass which changes the value of energy levels. The math form of the wavefunction is unchanged as one essentially has the same kind of differential equation for $W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt) W(x)$.

Approach of (1) Applied to a Infinite Square Well Potential

Equation ((3)) leads, for a free particle or solution in an infinite potential:

$$0 = \frac{p^2}{2m} - E - aE \frac{p^2}{m} \quad \text{or} \quad E(1 + \frac{p^2}{2m}) = \frac{p^2}{2m}$$

$$\text{Expanding as a power series: } E = \frac{p^2}{2m} (1 - \frac{p^2}{4mm} + \dots) = \frac{p^2}{2m} - \frac{p^4}{(8mmm)} + \dots \quad ((4))$$

Approach of (1) Applied to an Oscillator

In this case, the energy from ((3)) is, given $e_n = e_1 (n+0.5) \sqrt{k}$ and $e_n = e_1 / \sqrt{m}$

$$E = e_n [\sqrt{k(1 + (e_n/m)(e_n/m))} - e_n a m] \quad ((5))$$

e_n goes as $\sqrt{k/m}$ and $1/m$ is considered to be very small. This leads to:

$$\text{First Order: } E = e_n \quad (\text{power } 1/\sqrt{m}) \quad ((6a))$$

$$\text{Second Order: } e_1 \{ - 1/(4mm) m e_1/\sqrt{m} \} = (n+0.5)(n+0.5)k \cdot 0.25 \quad [m \text{ power}(-2)] \quad ((6b))$$

$$\text{Third Order: } e_1(1/32 \quad [m \text{ power } -3.5]) \quad ((6c))$$

One could obtain higher order corrections in both the infinite well and oscillator cases.

Approach of (2) for an Infinite Well Potential

The approach of (2) is to consider $W_{\text{relativistic}} = W_0 + W_1 + W_2$ etc where W_0 is the Schrodinger equation correction and W_1, W_2 , corrections representing different negative (not necessarily integer) powers of m . The d/dx derivative in the relativistic equation still applies to W_0, W_1, W_2 as argued in (2).

From (2) for the Klein-Gordon equation:

$$(e + de + m) (\text{power } 2) [W_0 + W_1 + W_2 + \dots] = - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} [W_0 + W_1 + W_2 + \dots] + mm (W_0 + W_1 + W_2) \quad ((7))$$

Here de is a correction to e (the nonrelativistic $p^2/2m$) and m is rest mass.

Note: W_0, W_1 and W_2 are considered to be weighted by different negative powers of m with $W_0 > W_1 > W_2$.

Then: $e^*e (W_0 + W_1 + \dots) + de^*de(W_0 + W_1 + \dots) + 2m(e+de)(W_0 + W_1 + \dots) + 2e de (W_0 + W_1 + \dots) = -d/dx d/dx (W_0 + W_1 + \dots) \quad ((8))$

Examining ((8)) de might be of order $1/(m^*m)$ or $1/(m^*m^*m)$ Now: $e^*e W_0 + 2m de W_0 = 0$ where $e = p^*p/2m$ is a possible solution leading to: $de =$ energy shift due to relativistic correction $= -\frac{1}{8} p^*p/(m^*m)$ which is the result obtained from an expansion of the full solution result from (2).

This matches the result from (1).

In (2) is shown that $W_2=0$ and $W_3 = -1/32 W_0$. Thus, the correction wavefunction piece W_2 has the same math form as W_0 .

Approach of (3) for an Oscillator

In (3), an equation from (4) for an oscillator is used, namely:

$$y \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} W + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dy} W + (k'/2 - \frac{1}{4} y) W = 0 \quad ((9))$$

with $k' = (E^*E - m^*m) / (2mw)$. (4) solves ((9)) exactly and yields:

$$E^*E = m^*m + 2(n+.5) mw \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{Thus: } E = e+m = m(1 + (n+.5) m^{-3/2} \sqrt{k} - (n+.5)^2 m^{-3} k + \dots) \quad ((11))$$

From ((11)), one may expand and obtain the first, second and third order values of energy (in addition to further orders). Here, however, we wish to apply the approach of (2) to the differential equation ((9)).

We first assume: $k' = 2me / 2mw = (e_0 + g)/w$ where g is unknown and $w = \sqrt{k/m}$ ((12))

As a first approximation, one may set $g=0$.

Thus, the terms of ((9)) represent different powers of m and one can break ((9)) into two equations, namely:

$$y \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} W - \frac{1}{4} y W = 0 \quad ((13)) \text{ and}$$

$$.5 \frac{d}{dy} W + k'/2 W = 0 \quad ((14))$$

From (3) (taken directly):

$$k' = [e^*e + 2me] / 2mw \text{ The next correction is: } e_0^*e_0/2mw + 2me_0/2mw + 2mg/2mw = e_0^*e_0/2mw + e_0/w + g/w$$

The $k'/2 W$ term is: $.5(e_0^*e_0/2mw + e_0/w + g/w) W$ but $W=W_0+W_1$ where W_0 is the Schrodinger result and W_1 a correction. The $k'/2 W$ terms becomes in the correction: $e_0^*e_0/4mw + 2mg/4mw + .5e_0/w W_1$ ((6)) This gives an order of $m^{-3/2}$ imposed by the first term ((5)) then becomes: $\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dy} W_1 + e_0^*e_0/4mw + 2mg/4mw + .5e_0/w W_1 = 0$ ((7)) W_0 is of the form $\exp(-ay)$ and $\exp(ky)$ form a basis. Thus, the terms with W_1 should cancel with each other and those with W_0 should do the same so: $e_0^*e_0/4mw + 2mg/4mw=0$ or $g = -\frac{1}{2} w^*w/m (n+.5)^2$ ((15))

In (3), we compute the next order term and show that it matches the third order term of (1).

Thus, the modified Schrodinger equation of (1) yields, at least to the first three orders, the same energy values as an expansion in negative (not necessarily integer) powers of m . The power expansion approach allows one to compute all orders of energy corrections and wavefunction corrections, but is obtained using a relativistic wavefunction, while (1) uses a modified nonrelativistic one.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (1) a modified Schrodinger equation is proposed which has an added $(\partial/\partial t \text{ grad dot grad } W)$ term and $a = 1/(4mm)$. This leads to a new nonrelativistic energy, but the math form of the wavefunction is the same as the non-modified Schrodinger equation, but with a modified mass.

In (2) and (3), we introduced an approach which involved using the Klein-Gordon relativistic equation, or another relativistic equation, and writing $W_{\text{relativistic}} = W_0+W_1+W_2\dots$ where W_0 represents the Schrodinger equation solution, and W_1, W_2 etc are corrections corresponding to expansions in negative (not necessarily integer) powers of m . One may obtain corrections to both the energy and wavefunction in this manner. In (2) we applied this approach to the infinite well and in (3), to the oscillator. Here, we show that the first three energy terms (0, first and second orders in a negative power of m expansion) match the first three expansion terms of the result from (1) and that the math form of the wavefunction, even with two correction terms is the same as the solution of the usual Schrodinger equation. For (1), the math form of the wavefunction is the same for the modified equation, because it only changes the mass term for a bound state.

References

- 1.
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relativistic Corrections to the 1D Schrodinger Equation for the Infinite Potential Well (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relativistic Correction to the Harmonic Oscillator in 1D (preprint, zenodo, 2019)

4.Rao, N. and Kagali, B. On the Energy Spectrum of the One Dimensional Klein-Gordon Oscillator <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0704.1869.pdf>